

THE EFFECT OF PERSONALITY TYPES ON STUDENTS SPEAKING PROFICIENCY

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Abstract: Extrovert Introvert personality types can not be denied in language learning, particularly, in oral performance. Extroverts are considered to be more proficient, while teachers struggle with how to approach introverted learners to show off their speaking skills. This paper investigates specific strengths and weaknesses of each type of student and how educators may involve and aid to improve the speaking skills of both types of learners.

Keywords: extroversion, introversion, speaking skills, oral proficiency, practice

1. Introduction

The language learning process is a complex process that various factors may affect the success or failure of the language learner. It is undeniable fact that the personality type of the learners' will affect their language learning. A great number of researches have been done so far in this area, meaning that this is an area of interest. There has been great importance of extroversion and introversion personality in achieving successful speaking skills. This case study aimed at analyzing how personality differences affect the learners' speaking proficiency in terms of pronunciation, lexical resource, accuracy, fluency, coherence & cohesion, and overall performance of the students (hesitation, eye contact, and confidence). It is interesting to discover the influence of personality traits on the learners' speaking performance. As for extrovert learners, they are considered to be social, easy-going people, in nature, this leads to effectiveness in their second language learning. However, Introvert

students are shy, closed, reserved compared to others which negatively impacts their language learning process (Dornyei, 2005). Therefore, I investigated whether or not there is any correlation between personality trait and their speaking proficiency. Being aware of students' personalities, whether they are extroverts or introverts, will help the teachers how to approach to develop their skills, in particular speaking performance. The results of his case study will be useful to determine where to stress while teaching speaking. I am definitely sure that my case study will be effective guideline to help teachers realize the students' strengths and weaknesses in their speech according to their personality and identifying how to approach extroverts and introverts. Even though there might be differences due to students' personality, the way they were taught may definitely effect their speaking skills. That is the point I should remember while conducting my case study.

2. Literature review

Personality: Extroversion & Introversion

The distinguishing features of students' personality characteristics will simultaneously affect their lives and their language learning process. Personality type is one of the essential reasons to impact their performance. The question of whether extroverts or introverts will help learners' language development or hinder their abilities has been answered by different researchers. Extroverts tend to socialize more, prefer action rather than thinking, whilst introverts are more likely to choose peaceful places and think silently (Campbell & Hawley, 1982). Therefore, introverted L2 learners may learn better if they are alone, as they tend to be socially anxious, in contrast, extroverted L2 learners might perform better if they work in groups (Cheek & Buss, 1981). Wilson and Lynn (1990) stated that classroom activities that demand individual working are the favor of introverts. Eysenck and Eysenck (1985) indicated that extroversion and introversion have a definite role in the second language study of the students. In relation to the personality traits, extroverts tend to recharge their battery

with high-energy parties, going out, while introverts do this by staying in and having a rest (Cain, 2013). Extroverts are eager to meet new people, like simulations (Parkash, et al,2016), while introverts prefer to read rather than ask it from others (Eyrinsk, 1987).

Personality and language learning

When it comes to learning, Extroverts learn best if they experience that process, they need to do more activities to understand what has been taught (Tieger & Barron-Tieger, 1995). The study in China showed that individual variables affect students' academic performance, introverts have higher results in receptive skills, while extroverts are ahead in speaking skills. However, there has been no difference identified in their writing performance (Zaved Khan, 2007). Similarly, research conducted by Zafar (2009) demonstrated that there has little difference in students' written works. However, introverts outperformed extroverts that are contradicting the conclusion of the research by plenty of psychologists (Rolfhus & Ackerman, 1999; SanchezMarin et al., 2001; Chamorro-Premuzic & Furnham, 2003). Regarding speaking, extroverts are considered to be better than introverts, as they tend to think out loud, they can think and speak simultaneously, formulate their ideas in the best way just by saying them confidently (Parkash, et al,2016). According to the investigation of Sheir (2015), the correlation between extroversion and introversion is obvious in terms of oral fluency in Palestine. The other study conducted by Sutin, Terracciano, and Zonderman (2011) also showed that emotionally stable, open students perform better in their oral performance by using the Five-Factor Model as an assessment tool. In stark contrast, when Eysenck Personality Questionnaire and interview were a tool for assessing, there was no significant difference in their oral performance (Aziz, 2010). This was such an interesting point that I choose this assessment tool in my case study thinking that there should be a difference whatever test form is used. This

literature review pointed out the main differences between extroverted and introverted students and helped to the further steps of this research paper.

3. Learner profile

Students and volunteer students of the other groups were chosen for this study. They study at Niners LC in Tashkent, Uzbekistan. In most language centers, students are divided according to their level with the help of placement test. However, as there were not enough amount of students for a homogenous class as there has been a quarantine period, my group is a heterogeneous class. The total number of students who are agreed to participate in this study is 9 (5 of them is mine), 4 males and 5 females, who have different language background from 3 to 10 years. (For this study I wanted to name participants as Student A to I, respectively) Their age is between 16-22 and their first language is the same (Uzbek). I tried to pay close attention to their background equality as much as I can, but their language level vary very much. Two of the students are A2 level learners, the other 7 students are B1 and B1+ learners. Almost all students know Russian except English and Uzbek (except student I). half of them know other languages like Tajik, Turkish and basic Arabic. Thus, I can call my participants are multilingual learners.

The majority of the participants were exposed to English at least 3 years before, only student I has been learning for 2 years and Student C has started very early, she said 10 years with gaps. In terms of how they learned English, I can say the methods I and my colleague implement in the classroom. I mostly use Communicative language teaching, paying more attention to interaction, my colleague pays attention to the vocabulary rather than grammar (this is the point I can not skip sometimes even if I have to do so), tries to find interesting texts to listen to and read for the students and encourage them to retell. That means he is more exposed to the Natural Approach. However, we will learn from each other, meaning that students are taught with a combination of the methods. But, the learners themselves claim that they are learning

utilizing the Grammar Translation Method in their school. Another point that should be mentioned here is that they all have the instrumental motivation that our learners are studying English for educational or work purposes. It is easy to achieve something if they have a target aim. All of them are learning to be students of the university or boost their career prospects. As for extracurricular activities, This education center initiates to organize movie days, speaking clubs, mini Ted talks, and invite native speakers to help our learners. They are grateful for such kinds of organizations.

I have been teaching them for almost three and half months. To my surprise, although they have different levels sometimes it is not much affecting their speaking performance, I mean, the student with a lower level can speak in her degree with confidence, but one-third of students speak lower level even they have more language learning period. Therefore, I attempted to investigate their personality type and its influence on their oral performance.

4. Research Design

In this section of the case study, I decided to gather data about personality types and their correlation to learners' speaking skills. The main aim of this study is to identify whether there is an effect of extroversion and introversion on the learners' oral performance. Firstly, I selected an assessment tool for separate students to extroverts and introverts. It was Eysenck's Personality Inventory (EPI) which measures extroversion-introversion and neuroticism-stability. It shows which one is dominant. It consists of 57 yes-no questions I paid attention to the only the first results (extrovert-introvert). Secondly, I took a 2 part interview. For the first part, I gave a topic card (IELTS part 2) asked them to speak for about 1 to 2 minutes about this topic. It was handful to analyze their speaking performance, in five categories (pronunciation, grammar, vocabulary, fluency, and overall speech (hesitation, confidence, eye contact). The task was to talk about a job they would not like to do and they should explain:

- what the job is

- where do you know it,
- whether it is easy or difficult
- why you do not like to do it. (adopted by ieltsmaterials.com)

Ultimately, I would like to ask 10 follow-up questions for the second part of my interview in order to be precise about their learning process. The attempt was made to the close analysis of their speaking to know learners' strength and weaknesses.

5. Data collection and analysis

The data collection stage started from student information questionnaire as I have mixed ability class.

	Gender	Age	Language Background	level
Student A	M	22	7	B1+
Student B	M	21	6	B1+
Student C	F	18	10	B1
Student D	F	18	4	A2+
Student E	M	19	3	B1
Student F	F	22	4	B1
Student G	F	21	7	B1+
Student H	F	16	7	B1+
Student I	M	16	2	A2

Table 1.

Afterwards, Eysenck's Personality Inventory (EPI) has been conducted for the second part of the research. The next thing I did is the calculation of the test results. This test helped me which student is the most extroverted and which student is the most introverted.

table 2.

As it is obvious from the graph Student A is the most extroverted one, showing 23 out of 24. Student G, however, is the most introverted one demonstrating, 4 out of 24. Looking at the results it is obvious 55% of the students are extroverted ones, while 45% of them are introverted learners. Only one third of them are the real introverts that there is no elements of the extroverts.

Afterwards, I checked their oral performance by means of two-part interview, for the first part I saw their speaking and analyses how they performed orally. Then, I gave a questions about their speaking performance. Here, the results are assessed on a scale of 1 to 10.

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I
Accuracy	8	7	6	5	6	7	8	8	5
Lexical recourse	8	7	6	7	6	6.5	7.5	8	5

Pronunciation	8.5	8	7	6	6	6.5	7	7.5	7
Fluency	8.5	8	6	5.5	6	7	6.5	7	6.5
Coherence/cohesion	7	6	7	6	5	6	7	7	5
Overall performance:	8	7.2	6.4	5.9	5.8	6.6	7.2	7.5	5.7
a. hesitation	-	-	+	-	+	-	+	-	+
b. confidence	+	+	-	+	-	+	-	-	-
c. eye contact	+	+	++	-	-	++	-	++	-

TABLE 3.

Looking at the given table, It is crystal clear that Student A performed the best. He has the highest score of extroversion, 8 out of 10. He is the most knowledgeable student in the classroom. So, difference cannot be obvious here. They all spoke as their level of vocabulary and grammar. But, in pronunciation extroverts struggle the most according to their level (Student D, E), contrasting to this, Students G,H and I showed higher results in their pronunciation level even they are introverted (7 and 7,5). In terms of fluency level, extrovert students are ahead , (proving the research of Parkash, 2016), even though, introverts showed lower results in some points, in their overall performance they are ahead sometimes from their extrovert partner (see Student B and Student G, H). Turning to the hesitation, Introverts were in doubt in terms of grammar sometimes, while extroverts continue their speech even they know their mistakes. As their extroversion level decreases, Students confident level has also a significant fall. Coming to the eye contact, Student A,B and C can keep it while introverts except Student H try to avoid.

Practicality.

In every teacher's classroom environment, they should keep a balance working with both extroverted and introverted students. We usually do not spend extra challenge for extroverted learners as they always raise their hands and love participation and group activities. But we cannot say the same for introverted students. Here are short practical ways to deal with introverted students:

- Silent speaking

Let learners to write what they are going to speak and then commence discussion.

- Think-Pair-Share

Most popular activity that every student can benefit. Ask students think individually about given questions, ask them discuss with their pair and share with group

- Use praises, at least, positive feedback, to give instrumental motivation

According to Cain (Cain,2012), shifting one's mindset and expectations before entering the classroom might be beneficial: classroom engagement can influence one's perception of class participation. If involvement is rewarded, some students will raise their hands solely for the purpose of speaking.

- Brainstorming or mind mapping before starting real speaking point

Giving a role for each member of the group when they are creating and presenting their mind maps can make wonders!

Conclusion.

As we discussed so far, extroverts are ahead in terms of fluency even they lack in their grammar or pronunciation. Introverts are more look like avoiding eye contact, but their overall performance is sometimes the same as their extrovert pairs. As it is a mixed class, it was difficult to analyze the real difference of the students. However, I come to the conclusion being an introverted student does not mean they cannot perform better. The main note for teachers is that "active participation my not be result for

effective language learning” (Ellis, 1994). There should be space for everyone to learn in their own pace. Moreover, there are far more other factors to consider for the effectiveness of oral performance ranging by the methods the teacher use, the level of the students, given feedback from the teacher, their learning styles. Even though, there seems to be a barrier for introverted learners, with well-implemented strategies they may overcome their challenges in speaking.

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